

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION
PART IV. PHOTO-CHEMICAL REDUCTION OF MOLYBDIC ACID SOL BY GLUCOSE, FORMALDEHYDE, ETHYL ALCOHOL, SODIUM HYPOPHOSPHITE, LEUCINE, GLUTAMIC ACID, AND α -ALANINE.

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The experimental arrangement was the same as before.

The sol was prepared from ammonium molybdate (Merck's reagent) and hydrochloric acid (Merck's reagent). Estimation of the reduced molybdic acid sol was carried out by spectrophotometric method using König-Martens spectrophotometer which was calibrated similarly as described in Part II. The absorption was noted in the green ($525 \mu\mu$). Results of calibration (*vide* Fig. 1) are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

Molybdate.	Zero-reading. θ_1	Final reading. θ_2	$\text{Log tan } \theta_2 - \text{log tan } \theta_1$
0.004 M	45°.0	72°.5	0.5013
0.0035	"	70°.5	0.4389
0.0030	"	67°.5	0.3828
0.0025	"	64°.0	0.3118
0.0020	"	60°.0	0.2386
0.0010	"	53°.5	0.1308

The concentration of the sol was expressed in terms of the molybdate used for the preparation of the sol and for calculating it the unit used was one-seventh of the molecular weight of the ordinary ammonium molybdate $[(\text{NH}_4)_6 \text{Mo}_7 \text{O}_{24} \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

Experimental Results.

Molybdc acid sol is not reduced by glucose, formaldehyde, alcohol, leucine, glutamic acid and α -alanine in the dark, but is reduced by hypophosphite in the dark when the p_{H} is below 3.9. In the case of hypophosphite the dark reaction begins instantaneously on mixing the sol with the reductant. The velocity of the dark reaction and the light reaction (in all cases) is zero-molecular with respect to the sol. The following is a special example for illustration.

TABLE II.

Leucine = 1%. Sol = 0.05M. $p_{\text{H}} = 2.46$. Temp. = 29.5°. $I_{\text{abs}} = 3150$ ergs/sq. cm./sec. (366 μ). d (thickness of the reaction cell) = 0.5 cm.

Time.	Spectrophotometric reading.	Conc. of reduced sol.	$K_{\text{zero-mol}} \times 10^3$.
(a) 0 min.	45°	...	...
(b) 30	49°5	$0.55 \times 10^{-3}M$	0.305 (from a & b)
(c) 46	56°0	1.35×10^{-3}	0.833 (from b & c)
(d) 62	61°2	2.08×10^{-3}	0.797 (from b & d)
(e) 73	65°0	2.65×10^{-3}	0.813 (from b & e)
			mean of the last three = 0.824

Induction Period.—All the reactions are attended with induction period. Passing nitrogen through the reaction mixture partially eliminated the induction period. In case of glutamic acid and α -alanine, the induction period is very high (3-4 hours) and it was overcome by exposing the reaction mixture first to the total radiation of the mercury lamp.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Reductant.

TABLE III A.

Temp.	I_{abs} (366 $\mu\mu$)	Molybdate.	p_H .	Conc. of reductant.	$K_s \times 10^3$.	γ .
$d = 0.5$ cm. $\gamma =$ Quantum efficiency.						
(a)				Formaldehyde.		
31°	307.7	0.018M	2.7	1.275M	0.275	1.48
"	"	"	"	0.85	0.194	1.03
"	"	"	"	0.43	0.119	0.63
(b)				Glucose.		
31°	483	0.028	1.7	20%	0.365	1.24
"	"	"	"	10	0.270	0.92
"	"	"	"	5	0.184	0.62
(c)				Leucine.		
29.5°	3150	0.05	1.78	2%	1.270	0.652
"	"	"	"	1.5	0.967	0.495
"	"	"	"	1	0.720	0.369
"	"	"	"	0.5	0.425	0.218
(d)				Glutamic acid.		
29.5°	3825	0.05	1.75	1%	0.202	0.085
"	"	"	"	0.667	0.152	0.064
"	"	"	"	0.333	0.088	0.037
(e)				α -Alanine.		
29.5°	2812	0.05	2.05	1%	0.168	0.097
"	"	"	"	0.667	0.108	0.062
"	"	"	"	0.333	0.058	0.033

$1/K$ plotted against $1/C_{\text{reductant}}$ gives a straight line in each case (Fig. 2).

TABLE III B.

Reductant used = Sodium hypophosphite. Temp. = 31°.

$$I_{\text{abs}} = 1696. \quad p_{\text{H}} = 1.80.$$

Molybdate.	Reductant.	$K_{\text{total}} \times 10^3$ (K_{t})	$K_{\text{dark}} \times 10^3$ (K_{d})	$K_{\text{light}} \times 10^3 =$ ($K_{\text{t}} - K_{\text{d}}$) $\times 10^3$.	γ .
0.05M	0.083N	0.867	0.350	0.517	0.485
"	0.0415	0.438	0.173	0.265	0.250
"	0.0207	0.210	0.082	0.128	0.121

The above data indicate that both the dark and light reactions are proportional to the concentration of the reductant.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Sol.

TABLE IV A.

Reductant used = 0.083M-Sodium hypophosphite. Temp. = 31°.

$$p_{\text{H}} = 2.15. \quad d = 0.5 \text{ cm.}$$

Molybdate.	I_{abs} (366 $\mu\mu$)	$K_{\text{total}} \times 10^3$ (K_{t})	$K_{\text{dark}} \times 10^3$ (K_{d})	$K_{\text{light}} \times 10^3 =$ ($K_{\text{t}} - K_{\text{d}}$) $\times 10^3$.	γ (366 $\mu\mu$).
0.1M	1578	0.742	0.317	0.425	0.485
0.075	1488	0.608	0.236	0.372	0.480
0.05	1257	0.483	0.167	0.316	0.393
0.025	1070	0.358	0.087	0.271	0.405

Therefore, it is evident that the quantum yield of the photochemical reaction is independent of the concentration of sol and the velocity of dark reaction is approximately proportional to the concentration of sol.

TABLE IVB.

$d=0.5$ cm.

Temp.	I	Molybdate.	ρ_w .	Reductant.	KO $\times 10^3$.	γ (366 μ)
(a)						
Formaldehyde.						
31°	570.7	0.018M	2.7	0.85M	0.488	1.40
"	662.5	0.036	"	"	0.569	1.41
(b)						
Glucose.						
31°	263.4	0.018	1.7	10%	0.148	0.92
"	333.7	0.027	"	"	0.188	0.92
"	380.4	0.036	"	"	0.214	0.92
(c)						
Leucine.						
29.5°	1575	0.01	1.24	1%	0.212	0.215
"	3150	0.05	"	"	0.442	0.226
"	3825	0.075	"	"	0.535	0.224
(d)						
α -Alanine.						
29.5°	1710	0.0125	2.05	1%	0.103	0.097
"	2317	0.025	"	"	0.143	0.099
"	2812	0.05	"	"	0.168	0.097
(e)						
Glutamic acid.						
29.5°	1912	0.0125	1.62	1%	0.085	0.072
"	2992	0.025	"	"	0.137	0.073
"	3825	0.05	"	"	0.180	0.075

In each case the quantum yield of the photochemical reaction is independent of the concentration of the sol.

Temperature Coefficient.

In all cases the temperature coefficient of the photochemical process $\left(\frac{K_{T+10}}{K_T}\right)$ is small being of the order of unity. The temperature coefficient of the dark reaction with hypophosphorous acid is of the order of 2 as will be evident from the following table.

TABLE V.

Sodium hypophosphite = 0.083*N*. $p_{\text{H}} = 1.63$.Molybdate = 0.05*M*. $I_{\text{abs}} = 1696$.

Temp	K_{total} (K_t)	K_{dark} (K_d)	$K_{\text{light}} =$ ($K_t - K_d$)	Temp. co-eff. (light reaction).	Temp. coeff. (dark reaction).
41°	1.683	0.962	0.722	1.02	2.04
31°	1.177	0.473	0.703	"	"

Variation of Intensity of Incident Radiation.

TABLE VI.

Temp.	I_{abs}	Molybdate.	p_{H}	Reductant.	$K \times 10^3$	$1/I_2$	$\frac{K_1}{K_2}$
a)							
Formaldehyde.							
31°	998.1	0.018 <i>M</i>	2.7	0.85 <i>M</i>	0.888	1.75	1.82
"	570.7	"	"	"	0.488		
b)							
Glucose.							
31°	482.9	0.018	1.7	10%	0.270	1.83	1.82
"	263.4	0.018	"	"	0.148		
c)							
Hypophosphite.							
31°	1246	0.05	1.85	0.0415 <i>N</i>	0.200	1.71	1.66
	727	"	"	"	0.120		
d)							
Leucine.							
29.5°	2475	0.05	2.28	1%	0.685	1.80	1.74
	1372	"	"	"	0.393		
e)							
α -Alanine.							
29.5°	2812	0.05	2.6	1%	0.215	1.75	1.86
"	1605	"	"	"	0.115		
f)							
Glutamic acid.							
29.5°	2812	0.05	2.31	0.667%	0.167	1.66	1.69
"	1687	"	"	"	0.098		

The rate of reaction under otherwise identical conditions is proportional to intensity of radiation absorbed.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—The quantum efficiencies of the process have been calculated exactly as done in Part II of this series and are given in Table IIIA.

Effect of Polarised Light (366 μ).

TABLE VII.

$d = 0.5$ cm.

Nature of light.	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	$K_0 \times 10^3$.	$K' \times 10^3$.
(a) Temp. = 31°. Formaldehyde = 0.85M. Molybdate = 0.018M. $p_{\text{H}} = 2.7$.			
Ordinary	570.7	0.489	0.066
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	76.8	0.066	
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	76.8	0.067	
(b) Temp. = 31°. Glucose = 10%. Molybdate = 0.018M. $p_{\text{H}} = 2.7$.			
Ordinary	482.9	0.296	0.048
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	76.8	0.051	
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	76.8	0.052	
(c) Temp. = 31°. Alcohol = 10.4M. Molybdate = 0.018M. $p_{\text{H}} = 2.7$.			
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	109.8	0.017	
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	109.8	0.018	
(d) Temp. = 29°.5. Lencine = 1%. Molybdate = 0.05M. $p_{\text{H}} = 2.13$.			
Ordinary	2475	0.663	0.116
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	433	0.116	
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	433	0.118	

K' in column (4) has been calculated for the intensity at which the reaction was carried in circularly polarised light, assuming that the velocity constant varies directly as the intensity of absorbed radiation.

From Table VII, it is evident that $V_0 = V_L = V_p$, the terms having the same significance as in Part II of this series.

DISCUSSION.

The reactions have the following characteristics :—

(1) It is zero-molecular with respect to sol and the concentration of the sol has got no influence on the quantum efficiency of the photochemical process.

(2) Zero-molecular velocity constant is proportional to the absorbed radiation.

(3) Maximum value of the quantum yield observed is practically unity.

(4) The inverse of velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of the reductant gives a straight line. (In case of hypophosphite, dark reaction is proportional both to the concentration of sol and that of hypophosphorous acid).

(5) Temperature coefficient of the velocity constant is unity

$$\frac{K_{T+10}}{K_T} = 1.02.$$

(6) *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light are equally effective (*cf.* reduction of tungstic acid sol; Part II).

All these characteristic features can be explained by the assumptions which were similar to that in the case of tungstic acid sol in Part II.

Unlike the reduction of tungstic acid sol, *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised lights are equally effective.

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